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IMPACT OF MODERNIZATION OF THE CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES ON THE ACTIVITY OF SOCIO-POLITICAL RELATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The economic, socio-political, and spiritual-ideological relations of Uzbekistan with the countries of Central Asia are analyzed socio-philosophically in the article. The conditions and factors affecting the formation of security, stability, and harmonious neighborhood environment in Central Asia are indicated. In the article, all the processes that take place in the socio-political system of social work proportionately, the activities of people in the socio-political processes are effective, the factors affecting their activation have an effect, the importance of Central Asia's rich natural resources, strategic location, economic transport, logistics issues, Uzbekistan's open and due to pragmatic policy, regional relations were restored, borders were opened, air, bus, and railway routes were restored, enriched with new routes, mutual relations between citizens were established, and it was analyzed that this had an impact on the development of economic and trade relations. Integrative processes in Central Asia are socio-philosophically analyzed as a holistic process consisting of interdependence, communication, and development process.

Keywords: Central Asia, modernization, integrative processes, economic, socio-political, spiritual-ideological relations, security, stability, friendly neighborly relations, conditions and factors affecting it.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада Ўзбекистоннинг Марказий Осиё давлатлари билан иқтисодий, ижтимоий-сиёсий, маънавий-мафкуравий алоқалари ижтимоий-фалсафий таҳлил қилинган. Марказий Осиёдаги хавфсизлик, барқарорлик ва аҳил қўшничилик муҳитини шакллантиришга таъсир кўрсатувчи шароит ва омиллар кўрсатиб ўтилган. Мақолада жамият ижтимоий-сиёсий тизимида содир бўладиган барча жараёнлар мутаносиб равишда ишлаши, кишиларнинг ижтимоий-сиёсий жараёнлардаги фаолияти самарали кечиши, уларнинг фаоллашувига таъсир этувчи омиллар таъсир кўрсатиши, Марказий Осиё ўзининг бой табиий ресурслари, стратегик жойлашуви, иқтисодий транспорт, логистика масалалари муҳимлигини, Ўзбекистоннинг очик ва прагматик сиёсати туфайли минтақавий алоқалар тиклангани, чегаралар очилиши, хаво, автобус, темир йўл йўналишлари қайта тиклангани, янги йўналишлар билан бойитилгани, фуқаролар ўртасидаги борди-келди муносабатлари йўлга қўйилгани, бу иқтисодий, савдо алоқаларининг ривожланишига ўз таъсирини кўрсатгани таҳлил қилинган. Марказий

Осиёдаги интегратив жараёнлар ўзаро боғлиқлик, алоқадорлик ва ривожланиш жараёнидан иборат бўлган яхлит жараён сифатида ижтимоий-фалсафий таҳлил қилинган

Калит сўзлар: Марказий Осиё, модернизация, интегратив жараёнлар, иқтисодий, ижтимоий-сиёсий, маънавий-мафқуравий алоқалар, хавфсизлик, барқарорлик, ахил қўшничилик муносабатлари, унга таъсир кўрсатувчи шароит ва омиллар.

Enter. The issue of strengthening the interregional cooperation of Uzbekistan with the countries of Central Asia is an important issue in foreign policy today. Uzbekistan is currently paying great attention to the development of mutually beneficial relations with the countries of Central Asia.

The most important priorities in the field of foreign policy of Uzbekistan are to strengthen the independence and sovereignty of the state, to increase the position and role of the country as an equal subject of international relations, to join the ranks of developed democratic states, to create an environment of security, stability and harmonious neighborhood around Uzbekistan. At the same time, strengthening the international prestige of the Republic of Uzbekistan, providing unbiased information to the world community about the reforms being carried out in the country, improving the normative and legal framework of the foreign political and economic activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the contractual and legal basis of international cooperation, solving the issues of delimitation and demarcation of the state border. issues such as these are topical issues today.

In the domestic and foreign policy of Uzbekistan, great attention is being paid today to building a stable, fair and democratic state, promoting the country's external transparency, and developing regional and multilateral cooperation.

Literature review

In the current period, a number of relevant program documents on the further development of multifaceted cooperation of Uzbekistan with the countries of Central Asia have been developed and adopted, and "road maps" have been approved. During the visits of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev and the heads of states of Central Asia at the highest and highest levels, attention is being paid to the issue of conducting an active, open, pragmatic and thoughtful foreign policy that meets the national interests of the countries..

Research methodology and empirical analysis

According to our firm belief, the readiness for practical cooperation and the earnest pursuit of it, as well as the feeling of responsibility for the common future of all Central Asian countries, are a solid foundation and guarantee of the region's stable development and prosperity, - says President Shavkat Mirziyoev, - Uzbekistan wants to solve controversial issues as soon as possible and mutually is in favor of further strengthening of trust. Based on the principles of good neighborliness and mutually beneficial cooperation, our countries can more effectively realize their potential in trade-economic, transport-communication, cultural-humanitarian spheres, security, and stability issues.

Uzbekistan's foreign policy initiatives are creating new opportunities for the entire of Central Asia. Uzbekistan is promoting an agenda for other countries in Central Asia, which consists of the idea of jointly solving existing problems. Today, Uzbekistan operates as a country that stabilizes the economic, social-political, spiritual-cultural, and ideological processes in Central Asia.

Currently, a new system of interstate relations is forming in Central Asia, and Uzbekistan is showing high activity in this system in various directions. As a result, signs of significant improvement in relations between the countries of the region are clearly visible. Uzbekistan has significantly expanded bilateral relations with Afghanistan, and actively joined multilateral efforts to resolve the Afghan problem. Uzbekistan is actively participating in the implementation of the major projects of the Surkhan-Puli-Khumri power transmission line and "Termiz-Mozori-Sharif-Peshawar" railway construction. An Educational Center for Afghan citizens was opened in Termez. Currently, Afghan students have graduated from this Educational Center, and some of them are working in the Afghan parliament, ministries, and institutions, teaching in the country's higher education institutions, and running independent businesses.

The volume of trade between Uzbekistan and the countries of Central Asia has doubled in recent years, and the number of joint ventures has increased 4 times. Our countries have signed

international documents such as ensuring radiation safety in Central Asia, "Water for Sustainable Development" actions, and the Ashgabat Declaration of the Energy Charter.

I would like to emphasize that our mutual rapprochement and expansion of cooperation in the region is a process that is demanded by the times and cannot be reversed, - says President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, - It is based on a strict political choice, has deep historical factors and is not directed against someone's interests. In this regard, by strengthening unity and cohesion, we contribute to the formation of our consistently and stably developing region, hence, a promising and reliable international partner.

An important priority of Uzbekistan in the field of foreign policy is the formation of a balanced system of strategic partnership and cooperation with the world's leading countries and international organizations. consists of

Uzbekistan is an important country in Central Asia and plays a special role. The importance of the country in the region is recognized by foreign experts and representatives of political circles. Uzbekistan signed an agreement on strategic cooperation with all neighboring countries in the region, which allows for high-level regional policy. The work carried out for these purposes is also important in strengthening the place and role of the country in the system of international relations. Uzbekistan's initiatives take into account the interests of all countries in Central Asia and are based on the principle of consensus. The new political reality in the region formed thanks to the active, proactive, and constructive diplomacy of Tashkent has had a positive effect on the strengthening of mutual actions on wide-ranging issues between the countries of Central Asia. An agreement was reached in Tashkent in November 2019 to discuss the solution to the issues arising between the countries of Central Asia. The holding of consultative meetings of Central Asian heads of state does not imply the establishment of a new international organization in the region or any integrated structure with its own charter and superior to state bodies. This activity envisages mutual agreement only on important issues of regional development.

The activation of Uzbekistan's focus on the region was a timely and practical response to the already-presented demand for regional rapprochement, restoration of trust and mutual understanding, as well as operational resolution of the accumulated issues based on reasonable compromises. A high level of open and reliable communication is essential to strengthening all areas of cooperation and establishing a foundation.

At the initiative of the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, political dialogues at the highest and higher levels have become significantly more active, and inter-parliamentary, inter-institutional, and inter-regional relations have been strengthened. In turn, during the mentioned period, all the heads of state of the region visited Uzbekistan. According to the analysis, the results of these meetings gave unprecedented results in terms of their effectiveness. Uzbekistan has reached a mutual agreement with all the countries of Central Asia on the joint fight against the activities of extremist and terrorist organizations. From July to September 2018, Uzbekistan conducted joint anti-terrorist exercises with Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan, and in 2019-2020, Uzbekistan signed relevant comprehensive action plans with Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. The work of Uzbekistan in the field of delimitation and demarcation of state borders with Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan has been advanced. All of this created an opportunity not only to resolve disputes between the states located in Central Asia bilaterally but also to remove acute conflict issues from the agenda of the entire region and increase the level of political trust.

Along with the activation of political cooperation between Uzbekistan and the countries of Central Asia, mutually beneficial relations and relations in trade-economic, transport-communication, energy, and cultural-humanitarian spheres have also increased somewhat.

The improvement of trade and economic relations between the countries of Central Asia helped to increase the investment attractiveness of the region, and from the beginning of 2017 until now, more than 300 contracts were signed between Uzbekistan and the countries of the Central Asian region, as well as about 75 billion. Contracts and agreements were signed in the amount of USD.

Progress is being observed among Central Asian countries in the field of solving environmental issues, including water and energy. Uzbekistan expressed its readiness to consider the

possibilities of its participation in the construction projects of Qambar-Ota and Rogun hydroelectric power stations. The implementation of an important section of the "Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan-Iran-Oman" transport corridor was started, and the "Turkmanabad-Forob" railway and road bridges were opened across Amudarya. Their launch made it possible to realize the idea of creating an intermediate transport and communication highway along the route "Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan-Caspian Sea-South Caucasus" with exits to the Black Sea ports of Baku-Tbilisi-Kars and Georgia, Turkey, Romania, and other countries.

After mutual negotiations between the countries of Central Asia, significant progress was made in the construction of a railway connecting China and Central Asia through Kyrgyzstan. According to preliminary estimates, when this project is implemented, cargo delivery times will be reduced by 7-8 days, and the road distance from East Asia to the countries of the Middle East and Southern Europe will be reduced by 900 km.

Result

At the present time, special attention is being paid to strengthening and expanding close cooperation, and friendly and close neighborly relations between Central Asian countries in the field of culture and humanitarianism.

I think that the creation of a platform for cultural and humanitarian exchange under the motto "Central Asia - a common past, a common future" meets the interests of all our peoples, - says President Shavkat Mirziyoev, - with your support, significant achievements in the fields of science, culture, and art. It is proposed to establish the Central Asia Award, as well as to organize university forums and regional sports games.

Ensuring peace and stability in Central Asia not only meets the interests of the countries of the region but also contributes to the stable development of the entire Eurasian continent in terms of its impact on the security of neighboring regions.

Summary

The Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Senate of the Oliy Majlis and the Legislative Chamber once again defined the priority directions of development of Uzbekistan in the near future, which includes fundamental reforms in the political, economic and social spheres, as well as the implementation of an active foreign policy. The modernized Uzbekistan has been demonstrating to the countries located in Central Asia its readiness for mutually beneficial cooperation, conducting an open, pragmatic and well-thought-out foreign policy that meets national interests. One of the most important issues in the foreign policy of Uzbekistan today is to bring the relations with the countries of the Central Asian region to a new level in terms of content and quality in the spirit of mutual friendship, good neighborliness and strategic partnership.

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